

PAPER A: RESEARCH ARTICLE

The Impact of Inclusive Finance on Economic Growth in Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of this work is to examine the influence of inclusive finance on economic growth in Nigeria between 2001 and 2021. Financial inclusion contributes to the reduction of poverty and the improvement of the standard of living of the people, making it a significant predictor of economic growth in developing countries. Methodology involves the use of Granger causality testing, the ordinary least square (OLS) regression model to estimate the coefficient of determination, R^2 , Unit Root Test, Cointegration Test and number of commercial banks' branches (NCBB) coefficient estimates. According to the NCBB coefficient estimates ($= -0.683$), for every thousand rise in the number of commercial bank branches, the GDP per capita will decline by around 0.683. The Unit Root Test using augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) results indicate that the series becomes stationary after the first difference, making it appropriate for further time series analysis, such as the cointegration test using Johansen's formula. The outcomes of the study lent support to the notion that monetary policy would be more effective if it promotes greater levels of financial inclusion.

External Link:

Keywords: Inclusive finance, GDP per Capita, Economic growth, Granger causality, Johansen formula, Unit root test

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1.0. | Introduction

Financial inclusion is defined as the provision of appropriate incentives to individuals to assist them in overcoming barriers that are critical to the achievement of stability and growth, the reduction of poverty, and the equitable distribution of resources and capabilities (Serrao et al., 2012). Financial inclusion is critical for the process of economic growth because, as more people are integrated into the formal financial system, it will aid in the right planning and decision-making process by providing more accurate and reliable data.

It also contributes to a reduction in the amount of money held outside of the banking sector. Financial inclusion is projected to accelerate economic growth and development by making funds available for investment and economic purposes that are hitherto unavailable. Utilizing and amassing these resources can result in a substantial quantity of low-cost, long-term investable wealth (Kama & Adigun, 2013). It entails integrating the informal financial realm into the mainstream financial system. Nwafor & Yomi (2018) emphasized that because low and middle-income earners make up the largest percentage of the population, they control a sizable portion

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of the economy's idle fund. However, because these funds are held in small amounts by each of the several million members of this group, harnessing and accruing these resources provides a massive source of cheap long-term investable capital. Most countries that have not effectively embraced financial inclusion are constructed in such a way that a significant amount of money flows into the informal sector, which is destructive to society and individuals (Gazdar & Cherif, 2014)(Kazeem, 2017). In terms of the person, the absence of financial inclusion leads the unbanked into informal banking sectors with high-interest rates and a limited supply of cash. Financial sector development contributes to poverty reduction in two mutually reinforcing ways. This is accomplished by the acceleration of economic growth and the provision of direct benefits to the poor. Financial inclusion must be quantified in terms of access to financial services (Yorulmaz, 2016).

According to Zulkhibri & Ghazal (2017), numerous studies on economic development and poverty reduction indicate that financial inclusion is critical. For example, empirical research indicates that increased access to financial benefits not only leads to growth but also income disparity and poverty reduction. Appropriate financial services have been shown to promote household welfare and stimulate small business growth (Yorulmaz, 2016)(Eton et al., 2019). Additionally, macroeconomic evidence indicates that economies with a greater degree of financial intermediation expand quicker and have less income disparity. This demonstrates the critical role of institutions in the financial intermediation process (Kazeem, 2017). Financial inclusion goals can be achieved mostly through the banking sector's initiative to reach across diverse strata of society, geographies, gender, and income levels and encourage the public to adopt banking habits (Akhil, 2016)(Wokabi & Fatoki, 2019). As a result, it is critical to act rapidly and collaboratively in pursuit of Nigeria's financial inclusion goals. Financial inclusion will increase participation in the formal financial system by increasing the amount of currency in circulation in the banking system, increasing credit available for productive purposes, and ultimately increasing GDP growth. Economic growth is a goal of financial inclusion, which also encompasses political, economic, and social inclusion, as pointed out by Aina & Oluyombo (2014) and Nalini & Mariappan (2012). Meanwhile, Abbas & Atanda (2019) stated that a review of the majority of scholarly submissions demonstrates that the purpose of financial inclusion is to boost economic growth by improving the economic well-being of people at the bottom of the pyramid and the unbanked by providing them with affordable financial services.

The Central Bank's five-year strategy (2019-2024) aims to attain a 95 per cent financial inclusion rate by 2024. The

implementation of the N50 tax would dissuade more individuals from utilizing mobile banking and hence contradict its purpose. You cannot afford to add such money if you wish to maintain your consumers. These developments have accelerated change in the financial services industry, injecting significant dynamism into the industry's value chain - altering how financial products and services are produced, delivered, and consumed. The regulators, led by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), have been at the forefront of establishing the Nigerian banking industry through the implementation of the Nigerian Sustainable Banking Principles (NSBP), which has facilitated the establishment of the Nigerian banking industry. According to Akhil (2016), financial inclusion is defined as the provision of affordable financial services to the poor, while El Said et al. (2020) argued that financial inclusion refers to households' and businesses' access to and use of financial products and services, which is critical, albeit challenging priority in Emerging Markets (EMs) and a critical factor in financial development. Financial inclusion, economic development, and growth are inextricably linked. According to Zulkhibri & Ghazal (2017), financial inclusion (FI) is seen as a critical tool for addressing poverty and inequality and achieving sustainable development goals within the broader context of inclusive development (SDGs). Abbas & Atanda (2019) said that the strength of scholarly submissions stems from the fact that financial inclusion is critical for the economic process of any country, including Nigeria because it enables policymakers to conduct sound planning and decision-making. Financial inclusion, according to the Nigerian Financial Inclusion Strategy (NFIS 2018), is achieved when adult Nigerians have easy access to a comprehensive range of formal financial services that satisfy their needs and are inexpensive.

Martin (2008) compared the financial exclusion rate in Switzerland, the United States, Venezuela, Nigeria, Pakistan, India, and Argentina over a four-and-a-half-decade period (1960-2005) using the same measure of the ratio of currency outside the banking system to the limited money supply. There appears to be a lot of variation in financial inclusion across countries, and some commitments and policies have been difficult to implement (Anyanwu et al., 2018). Financial inclusion in Nigeria increased from 36.3% in 2010 to 43.3% in 2012, 48.6% in 2014, and 48.6% in 2016, while the number of Nigerians banking with a bank increased from 30% in 2010 to 32.5% in 2012, 36% in 2014, and 38.3% in 2016 (based on World Bank data). Other service providers, such as microfinance banks, insurance companies and pension funds, grew by 6.3% between 2010 and 2016. Meanwhile, it is estimated that the informal sector (which includes non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and financial cooperatives) shrank from 17.4% of the economy in 2010 to 9.8% of the economy by 2016. However, the main objective of this research is to

ascertain the effect of inclusive financing on Nigeria's economic growth. To achieve this, the work outlines involve, determining the level of inclusive finance and economic growth, examining the relationship between inclusive finance and economic growth, studying the impact of inclusive finance indicators on the economic growth of Nigeria, investigating the causal relationship between inclusive finance variables and economic growth and proffer possible recommendations.

2.0. | Methodology

2.1. | Data and Methods

The data used for this study were GDP per Capita, currency in circulation (CIC), number of commercial banks' branches (NCBB), rural banks' depositors (RBD), banks' credit to private sector (CPS) extracted from World Bank publication and CBN Bulletin from a period of 2001 to 2021.

The method of analysis used for this work was divided into three parts namely, descriptive statistics, ordinary least square regression analysis and time series analysis (using unit root test, Johansen cointegration and Granger causality test). The statistical software used for this study were EViews version 11.0 and STATA version 16.0.

2.2. | Model Specification

The formulated hypothesis was tested using the functional description of the model, which is (Eqn. 1)

$$\text{GDP per Capita} = f(\text{CIC}, \text{NCBB}, \text{RBD}, \text{CPS}) \quad (1)$$

Decision rule which stipulates that the null hypothesis should be rejected if $P < \alpha$ and accepted if otherwise was adhered to; where α is the significant level (1%, 5%, 10% respectively).

The ordinary least square regression model with response or dependent variable Y and its regressors or independent variables or predictors was specified in Eqn. 2.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_3 x_3 + \beta_4 x_4 + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

Eqn. 2 was re-expressed into Eqn. 3,

$$\text{GDP per Capita} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{CIC} + \beta_2 \text{NCBB} + \beta_3 \text{RBD} + \beta_4 \text{CPS} + \varepsilon_i \quad (3)$$

where, Y = response or dependent variable, X_1 to X_4 = the independent variables or predictors and ε_i = the error term.

The model was shortened as shown in Eqn. 4.

$$y = x\beta + \varepsilon \quad (4)$$

The resulting ordinary least square (OLS) estimator of β 's was expressed in form of Eqn. 5.

$$\beta = (x'x)^{-1}x'y \quad (5)$$

Given the OLS estimator, the dependent variable was predicted by $y = x'i\beta$ and the error term by $e_i = y_i - x'i\beta$; where e_i is called the residual.

Furthermore, the goodness of fit of an OLS regression was measured using Eqn. 6,

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{SSR}{SST} = \frac{SSE}{SST} \quad (6)$$

where $SST = \sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2$ is the total sum of squares, $SSR = \sum e_i^2$ = the residual sum of squares (to minimize residual error), and $SSE = \sum(\hat{y}_i - \bar{y})^2$ = the explained sum of squares.

The coefficient of determination, R^2 , lies by definition, between 0 and 1 and reports the fraction of the sample variation in y explained by the x 's.

It must be noted that, R^2 increases by construction with every (also irrelevant) additional regressors and is therefore not a good criterium for the selection of regressors. The adjusted R^2 , given in Eqn. 7, is a modified version that does not necessarily increase with additional regressors.

$$adj. R^2 = 1 - \left[\frac{(1-R^2)(n-1)}{n} - (k+1) \right] \quad (7)$$

Where n = the number of points in the data set and k = the number of independent variables from the model, excluding the constant (Abubakar et al., 2022).

2.3. | Model Diagnostic Check

The constructed model for this research is regression model and it is a parametric test predicting the economic growth in Nigeria (GDP per Capita). Dependent variable is GDP per Capita, being the measure of the economic growth, while the independent variables are inclusive finance variables which are currency in circulation, rural banks' depositors, and banks' credit to private sector.

The normality and multicollinearity check are necessary to ensure the model is reliable and robust. Multicollinearity usually caused a misleading R^2 and P-values (that is, misleading results) if present. The Shapiro-Wilk test (Razali & Wah, 2011) was performed to test for normality of the data set and variance inflation factor (VIF) which is the indicator

for the checks of multicollinearity (O'Brien, 2007). If VIF is less than 5 ($VIF < 5$), it means the model does not suffer from the problem of multicollinearity. However, for normality, the null hypothesis strictly state that the data is normally distributed when it is accepted (that is, $P > 0.05$) and not normally distributed if rejected. Stata 16.0 is the computer software used in this write-up.

2.4. | Justification of Method

For the purpose of investigating the impact of inclusive finance on economic growth in Nigeria, secondary data is needed since it is difficult to get first-hand information on the variables used. Ordinary least regression was also considered suitable in view of the fact that it helps in not only establishing relationship between variables, but causes an effect with support of Granger Causality Test. In order to achieve reliability of the result, robustness tests like multicollinearity test, heteroscedasticity test and normality test were also conducted. Model specification is to justify that the numbers of independent variables which are continuous are regressed against the dependent (continuous) variable and to study the independent variables that have significant effect on the dependent variable.

2.5. | Unit Root Test

The unit root test, also known as the stationarity test, indicates the presence of a unit root if the series lacks stationarity and may lead to spurious results and the absence of a unit root if the series does have stationarity. So, to avoid the problem of spurious results, the unit root test was accomplished through the use of the augmented Dickey-Fuller Test (ADF). The hypothesis to accomplish the unit test was stated as follows.

“Ho: there is a presence of a unit root (series is not stationary) vs Ha: there is no unit root (the series is stationary).”

The ADF test is mathematically presented in Eqn. 8,

$$\Delta Y_t = \theta + \gamma Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i Y_{t-i} + \omega_t \quad (8)$$

where, θ = constant, γ = the coefficient of process root, β_i = coefficient in time tendency, p = the lag order, and ω_t = the disturbance (error) term.

2.6. | Granger Casualty Test

The Granger causality test was used to analyze the causal link of the variables, focusing primarily on the causal relationship among the variables of interest (Eichler, 2012). X causes Y ($X \rightarrow Y$) or X is related to Y ($X \rightarrow Y$), are two hypothetical

examples. This research looks at whether X causes Y or otherwise. The Granger causality test will also disclose the impact of inclusive finance on economic growth in Nigeria.

Granger causality is a time series causality approach used for prediction, where there are two time series X and Y using vector autoregression (VAR) model.

The VAR model is made up of two equations, namely, Eqn. 9 and Eqn. 10.

$$y_t = c_1 + \sum^3 i = 1\alpha_1, iy_{t-i} + \sum^3 i = 1\beta_1, ix_{t-i} \varepsilon_{x, t} \quad (9)$$

$$y_t = c_2 + \sum^3 i = 1\alpha_2, iy_{t-i} + \sum^3 i = 1\beta_2, ix_{t-i} \varepsilon_{x, t} \quad (10)$$

For testing Granger Causality,

- ❖ The null hypothesis of non-causality ($\beta_{2,1} = \beta_{2,2} = \beta_{3,3} = 0$) was tested
- ❖ The Wald test statistic follows a χ^2 distribution
- ❖ The null hypothesis was rejected if P-value is less than the significant level (i.e. $P < \alpha$).
- ❖ The test should be both directions, which is $X \Rightarrow Y$, and $X \Leftarrow Y$.

2.7. | Johansen Cointegration Test

Johansen cointegration test is an approach for testing cointegration of integrated series with zero level $I(0)$ or of order 1, $I(1)$ - after first difference (Johansen & Katarina, 2001). This test permits more than one cointegrating relationship. So, it is more generally applicable than Engle-Granger test which is based on the Dickey-fuller (or augmented) test for unit root. There are two types of Johansen test which are the trace and max Eigen value, and they form the basis of the inference or decision and their result might be little different from other. When the VAR model (Eqn. 11) indicated by Var(p) is mathematically defined in a general term below as,

$$y_t = a + \beta_1 y_{t-1} + \beta_2 y_{t-2} + \dots + \beta_p y_{t-p} + e_t \quad (11)$$

It is important to note that the variables should be stationary before proceeding to Johansen Cointegration test.

3.1. | Results and Interpretation

Table 1 shows that GDP per Capita ($M = 84.90$, $SD = 10.50$) implies that on average, GDP per Capita represent about 84.9% with variability of 10.5%. CIC ($M = 63.19$, $SD = 8.4$) means that currency in circulation represent about 64.19 billion naira on average with variability of 8.4 billion naira.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Observations	Mean	Standard Deviation
GDP per Capita	21	84.90	10.50
CIC	21	63.19	8.40
NCBB	21	12.71	3.00
RBD	21	11.86	2.49
CPS	21	51.38	7.23

Source: Author’s Computation using Stata Software

NCBB (M = 12.71, SD = 3.00) indicate that number of commercial banks’ branches represent about 12.71 thousand on average with variability of 3 thousand branches. RBD (M = 11.86, SD = 2.49) means that on average, rural commercial banks depositor is about 11.86 billion naira with variability of about 2.49 billion naira and CPS (M = 51.38, SD = 7.23) banks credit to private sector on average represent about 51.38 billion naira with variability of about 7.23 billion.

Table 2 shows that GDP per Capita (P<0.01, I(1)), NCBB (P<0.01, I(1)), CPS (P<0.01, I(1)), CIC (P<0.01, I(1)) and RBD (P<0.01, I(1)) which means that gross domestic product per

capita, number of commercial banks’ branches, banks’ credit to private sector, currency in circulation, and rural banks’ depositor are statistically significant at 1% and becomes stationary after the first difference.

Table 2: Unit root test (Augmented Dickey fuller)

Differenced Variable	Test Statistic	P-value	Order
GDP per Capita	-5.581	0.0003*	I(1)
NCBB	-7.477	0.0000*	I(1)
CPS	-7.327	0.0000*	I(1)
CIC	-6.539	0.0000*	I(1)
RBD	-8.297	0.0000*	I(1)

Asterisk * represent 1% level of significance

Source: Authors Computation using E-Views

This tells us that the series are integrated of order one (I (1)). This suggest that we can now proceed with further times series analysis like cointegration and causality test as specified in the methodology chapter. Table 3 is the outcome of the Johansen test for cointegration.

Table 3: Johansen Test for Cointegration

Trend: constant Sample: 2003 -2021			Number of obs. = 19 Lag = 2		
Maximum Rank	Parameters	LL	Eigen value	Trace Statistic	5% Critical Value
0	30	-274.528	-	99.5053	68.52
1	39	-252.546	0.90113	55.5406	47.21
2	46	-240.355	0.72285	32.1600	29.68
3	51	-231.859	0.59113	14.1673*	15.41
4	54	-226.478	0.43247	3.4047	3.76
5	55	-224.775	0.16406		

Source: Author’s Computation using Stata Software

Table 3 clearly reveals that maximum rank order (0-2) of the three cointegrating equations trace statistic value are more than the critical value at 5% level of significance (trace statistic >5% critical value), which indicate that there is strong evidence of cointegration among the series (gross domestic product per capita, number of commercial banks’ branches, banks’ credit to private sector, currency in circulation, and rural banks’ depositor) and this suggest that there is a long run relationship among gross domestic product per capita, number of commercial banks’ branches, banks’ credit to private sector, currency in circulation, and rural banks’ depositor. This simply tells us that there is a long run relationship between inclusive finance and economic growth in Nigeria.

Fig. 1, 2 and 3 shows that gross domestic per capita have the highest growth level among all the five variables of interest while rural banks’ depositor has the lowest growth level – and this agrees with the situation on ground according to the findings of EFINA survey and contributed to high rate of unbanked among the rural residents as they lack financial education and are even not sensitive to financial technology, where which they can access finance easily.

Figure 1: Bar Chart Showing the Mean of GDP per Capita, CIC, NCBB, RBD, and CPS

Figure 2: Box plot showing the distribution of GDP Per capita, CIC, NCBB, RBD, and CPS

Figure 3: Line Graph Showing the Distribution of GDP per Capita, CIC, NCBB, RBD, and CPS

Meanwhile, the line graph in Fig. 3 showing the distribution of gross domestic product per capita, number of commercial banks’ branches, banks’ credit to private sector, currency in circulation, and rural banks’ depositor implies that they are not stationary.

Table 4 shows that the fitted OLS regression model ($P < 0.01$) indicates that the model is statistically significant at 1% which indicate that there is a significant relationship between gross domestic product per capita, number of commercial banks’ branches, banks’ credit to private sector, currency in circulation, and rural banks’ depositor.

Table 4: Ordinary least square (OLS) Regression analysis

Variables	Coefficient Estimate	STD Error	Test Statistic	P-value
GDP per Capita				
CIC	0.687	0.278	2.47	0.025**
NCBB	-0.683	0.497	-1.37	0.188
RBD	1.334	0.641	2.08	0.054***
CPS	0.181	0.310	0.58	0.568
Constant	25.051	12.867	1.95	0.069
Model P-value	0.0005			
R^2	0.6962			
Adj. R^2	0.6202			

where asterisk *** and ** are 10% and 5% significant level respectively

Source: Author’s Computation using Stata Software

$R^2 = 0.6962$ implies that, about 70% variation in economic growth (gross domestic product per capita) can be explained by financial inclusion indicators (number of commercial banks’ branches, banks’ credit to private sector, currency in circulation, and rural banks’ depositor). The R^2 is relatively high and the model is statistically significant which suggest that the model is a good fit for the data and is very suitable for future prediction of economic growth in Nigeria.

Meanwhile, CIC ($\beta = 0.687, P < 0.05$) indicate that currency in circulation is statistically significant at 5% level and have positive significant impact on GDP per Capita. RBD ($\beta = 1.334, P < 0.10$) implies that rural banks’ depositor is statistically significant at 10% level and have positive significant impact on economic growth (GDP per Capita). Besides, the coefficient estimates of NCBB ($\beta = -0.683$) tells us that... for one thousand increase in the number of commercial banks’ branches, the GDP per Capita will decrease by about 0.683 which agrees with the work of Mbutor & Uba (2013). The study’s findings supported the idea that monetary policy would be more effective if it increased financial inclusion. As a result, there are clusters of

underutilized bank branches that have a negative coefficient, which can be explained by the fact that banks open branches for profit rather than financial inclusion, a policy goal. **Table 5** is obtainable, the Granger Causality P-values.

Table 5: Granger Causality

Equation	Excluded	Causal direction	P-value
GDP per Capita	CIC	GDP per Capita→CIC	0.155
GDP per Capita	NCBB	GDP per Capita→NCBB	0.518
GDP per Capita	RBD	GDP per Capita→RBD	0.316
GDP per Capita	CPS	GDP per Capita→CPS	0.148
GDP per Capita	ALL	GDP per Capita→ALL	0.289
CIC	GDP per Capita	CIC→GDP per Capita	0.008*
CIC	NCBB	CIC→NCBB	0.113
CIC	RBD	CIC→RBD	0.267
CIC	CPS	CIC→CPS	0.459
CIC	ALL	CIC→ALL	0.058***
NCBB	GDP per Capita	NCBB→GDP per Capita	0.834
NCBB	CIC	NCBB→CIC	0.001*
NCBB	RBD	NCBB→RBD	0.181
NCBB	CPS	NCBB→CPS	0.200
NCBB	ALL	NCBB→ALL	0.000*
RBD	GDP per Capita	RBD→GDP per Capita	0.188
RBD	CIC	RBD→CIC	0.032**
RBD	NCBB	RBD→NCBB	0.187
RBD	CPS	RBD→CPS	0.004*
RBD	ALL	RBD→ALL	0.017**
CPS	GDP per Capita	CPS→GDP per Capita	0.017**
CPS	CIC	CPS→CIC	0.197
CPS	NCBB	CPS→NCBB	0.094***
CPS	RBD	CPS→RBD	0.298
CPS	ALL	CPS→ALL	0.031**

where asterisk *** ** and * are 10%, 5% and 1% respectively

Source: Author’s Computation using Stata Software

Table 5 shows that currency in circulation (CIC), number of commercial banks’ branches (NCBB), rural banks’ depositors (RBD) and banks’ credit to private sector (CPS) have a significant causal relationship with economic growth (GDP per Capita). This tells us that there is a significant causal relationship between the inclusive finance indicators and economic growth.

4.1.1. | **Normality Test**

Fig. 4 shows the normality test by Shapiro-Wilk ($P > 0.05$) and its graphical illustration which indicates that the data is normally distributed at 5% level which satisfies the normality assumption of the fitted model.

Figure 4: Shapiro-Wilk ($P = 0.9574$)

Table 6 shows that all the predictor variables (currency in circulation, banks' credit to private sector, rural banks' depositor and number of commercial banks' branches) have variance inflation factor (VIF) that is less than 5 ($VIF < 5$) which indicate that the model does not suffer from the problem of multicollinearity and this make it a robust and reliable model.

Table 6: Multicollinearity

Predictor variables	VIF	1/VIF
CIC	2.60	0.384552
CPS	2.40	0.415909
RBD	1.22	0.819560
NCBB	1.06	0.942189
Mean VIF	1.82	

Table 7 shows that $P > 0.05$ for both the test for heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation which means that the fitted OLS model does not suffer from the problem of autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity. This also satisfy the ordinary least square (OLS) assumptions.

Table 7: Heteroscedasticity and Autocorrelation

Test	Chi-square Statistic	P-value
Heteroscedasticity	1.21	0.2709
Autocorrelation	0.27	0.6015

3.2. | Discussion/Summary of Findings

Table 1 shows that GDP per Capita ($M = 84.90, SD = 10.50$) implies that on average, GDP per Capita represent about 84.9% with variability of 10.5%. While CIC ($M = 63.19, SD = 8.4$) in the table means that currency in circulation represent about 64.19 billion naira on average with variability of 8.4 billion naira, NCBB ($M = 12.71, SD = 3.00$) indicate that number of commercial banks' branches represent about 12.71 thousand on average with variability of 3 thousand branches, RBD ($M = 11.86, SD = 2.49$) means that on average, rural commercial banks depositor is about 11.86 billion naira with variability of about 2.49 billion naira and CPS ($M = 51.38, SD = 7.23$) banks credit to private sector on average represent about 51.38 billion naira with variability of about 7.23 billion.

Table 2 shows that GDP per Capita ($P < 0.01, I(1)$), NCBB ($P < 0.01, I(1)$), CPS ($P < 0.01, I(1)$), CIC ($P < 0.01, I(1)$) and RBD ($P < 0.01, I(1)$) which means that gross domestic product per capita, number of commercial banks' branches, banks' credit to private sector, currency in circulation, and rural banks' depositor are statistically significant at 1% and becomes stationary after the first difference. This tells us that the series are integrated of order one ($I(1)$). This suggest that

times series analysis like cointegration and causality test can be proceeded forthwith.

Table 3 clearly reveals that maximum rank order (0-2) of the three cointegrating equations trace statistic value are more than the critical value at 5% level of significance (trace statistic $> 5\%$ critical value) which indicate that there is strong evidence of cointegration among the series (gross domestic product per capita, number of commercial banks' branches, banks' credit to private sector, currency in circulation, and rural banks' depositor) and this suggest that there is a long run relationship among gross domestic product per capita, number of commercial banks' branches, banks' credit to private sector, currency in circulation, and rural banks' depositor. This simply tells us that there is a long run relationship between inclusive finance and economic growth in Nigeria.

Table 5 shows that currency in circulation (CIC), number of commercial banks' branches (NCBB), rural banks' depositors (RBD) and banks' credit to private sector (CPS) have a significant causal relationship with economic growth (GDP per Capita). This tells us that there is a significant causal relationship between the inclusive finance indicators and economic growth.

Besides, **Table 4** shows that the fitted OLS regression model ($P < 0.01$) indicate that the model is statistically significant at 1% which indicate that there is a significant relationship between gross domestic product per capita, number of commercial banks' branches, banks' credit to private sector, currency in circulation, and rural banks' depositor. $R^2 = 0.6962$ implies that 69.62% variation in Economic growth (gross domestic product per capita) can be explained by financial inclusion indicators (number of commercial banks' branches, banks' credit to private sector, currency in circulation, and rural banks' depositor). The R^2 is relatively high and the model is statistically significant which suggest that the model is a good fit for the data and is very suitable for future prediction of economic growth in Nigeria.

Meanwhile, CIC ($\beta = 0.687, P < 0.05$) indicate that currency in circulation is statistically significant at 5% level and have positive significant impact on GDP Per capita. RBD ($\beta = 1.334, P < 0.10$) implies that rural banks' depositor is statistically significant at 10% level and have positive significant impact on economic growth (GDP Per capita). Besides, the coefficient estimates of NCBB ($\beta = -0.683$) tells us that for one thousand increase in the number of commercial banks' branches, the GDP per Capita will decrease by about 0.683 which agrees with the work of Mbutor & Uba (2013). The study's findings supported the idea that monetary policy would be more effective if it increased financial inclusion. As a result, there

are clusters of underutilized bank branches that have a negative coefficient, which can be explained by the fact that banks open branches for profit rather than financial inclusion, a policy goal.

However, the model assumptions test shows that the data is normally distributed and the model does not suffer from the problem of multicollinearity, autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity which means the model is very robust and reliable.

4.1. | Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that currency in circulation and rural bank depositors have a positive and significant impact on economic growth, and as a result, it was concluded that the provision of banking services in rural areas will contribute positively to Nigeria's economic growth. Accepting deposits and granting loans are two of the most common types of financial services. The granger causality also shows that there is a significant causal relationship between financial inclusion and economic growth. Johansen cointegration indicate that there is a long run relationship between financial inclusion and the economic growth of Nigeria. The currency in circulation, which is a component of Nigeria's limited money supply, has had a favorable impact on the country's economic growth. Because of the flow of currency through banking transactions, economic activities have been stimulated, resulting in an improvement in the overall state of Nigeria's economic development.

Furthermore, according to the NCBB's coefficient estimates, for every thousand increase in the number of commercial bank branches, the GDP per capita will decline by around 0.683, which is consistent with the findings of Mbutor and Uba's research (2013). The outcomes of the study lent support to the notion that monetary policy would be more effective if it promoted greater levels of financial inclusion. The outcome is a concentration of underutilized bank branches with a negative coefficient, which can be explained by the fact that banks open branches for profit rather than to promote financial inclusion, which is a governmental goal.

4.2. | Recommendations

As a result of the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- ❖ To achieve the desired level of money supply, the monetary authorities must implement policies to ensure that a substantial proportion of the money supply is made up of currency in circulation. This will reduce the quantity of money held outside of banks. For economic

growth to continue, rural bank branches should be encouraged to make loans to private businesses and small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

- ❖ In order to encourage depositors and savers, rural bank branches should be given the ability to do so. As a result, deposits will be encouraged, and economic growth will be improved. When creating their business models, banks should keep in mind their commitment to sustainability to ensure that they can cope with disruptions and have a good environmental and social impact in their effort to give value to their stakeholders. In order to withstand disruptive events, banks and other financial institutions must completely adopt sustainability principles, the authors argue, noting that this is especially more crucial during periods of substantial disruption, such as the coronavirus epidemic (COVID-19)
- ❖ During the pandemic, the financial services industry was undergoing considerable transformation. Banks have had to adapt their business models in response to changes brought about by innovation, digitization, new entrants from the Fintech sector, more regulation, and shifting needs and behavioral patterns among their clients.
- ❖ The government and monetary authorities should ensure that banking services are promoted and that bank branches are established in more rural areas, as well as that these banks be given equitable assistance in order to satisfy the needs of these areas efficiently.

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	Formal Analysis	X
	Acquisition of Funds	X
	Research	X
	Methodology	X
	Project Management	X
	Means	X
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	Writing-revision and editing	X
	Discussion of Result	X
	Review and approval of the final version	X

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